

MOISTURE ABSORPTION IN VOIDED POLYMER COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The objective of this research was to investigate the relationship between void content and moisture uptake in a carbon fibre/epoxy resin system. Void contents in the range 0.5-2.5% were produced by varying the cure cycle and the effect on moisture uptake established by a controlled weighing programme. It was found that whereas there was a determinable link between moisture uptake and void content, anomalies occurred. These were attributed to the location of voids within the composite. C-scan, which takes account of both surface and bulk effects gave a better correlation with moisture uptake than void content as measured by image analysis.

KEYWORDS: carbon/epoxy, moisture absorption, voids, void measurement, c-scan, image analysis

INTRODUCTION

A major factor which limits the performance of composite materials is the presence of defects which are produced during manufacture; the most common being voids or porosity. The presence of such defects has a marked effect on the mechanical properties and the effect is proportional to void content [1].

Voids and defects also affect moisture absorption, saturation levels, diffusivity and mass gain [2,3]. The latter is especially important with sandwich panels which will not readily release moisture which has been absorbed. Considering that mass is so important to the aerospace industry, it is surprising that comparatively little research has been undertaken to establish the relationship between void content and moisture uptake.

The objective of this work was to investigate this relationship for a typical carbon fibre/epoxy aerospace composite system. The cure cycle was altered to give voidage in the range 0% - 2.5%.

EXPERIMENTAL

Panels

Nine, eight ply, panels were produced using woven carbon cloth and an epoxy resin system containing 30% thermoplastic (ICI-977-2). The normal cure cycle to produce a low voidage product involves heating at 2°C/min to the cure temperature of 185°C. The variation in the void

levels was achieved by altering the times at which the pressure was applied during the cure cycle. By keeping cure temperatures and times constant it was ensured that the other important variables such as degree of cure, dimensions and fibre volume fractions would be unaffected and hence not influence the objectives of this research. The only possible exception was panel A which included an additional dwell at 145°C. A brief summary of the cure cycles amendments is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Cure cycle amendments

PANEL	CURE CYCLE AMENDMENTS
G	Control Panel (as manufacturer's spec.)
I	No compaction pressure
C	No vacuum
D	Pressure applied at t=40 min
F	Pressure applied at t=70 min
E	Pressure applied at t=80 min
H	Pressure applied at t=110 min
B	Vacuum maintained to t=70 min
A	Extra dwell period at t=65 min

Assessment of Panel Quality and Voidage

Accurate measurement of void content at levels below 2% is difficult. Image analysis is destructive and time consuming, but with increased operator skill can give an accurate assessment of bulk voidage and void distributions. Hence, although not ideal from a practical standpoint, image analysis was used in order to establish void levels. Coupons (four from each panel) were cut and carefully prepared and polished to a 1µm finish prior to assessment using Vista Image Analysis.

From an industry standpoint, assessment by non-destructive methods such as ultrasonics is a more attractive option. Hence, the panels were C-scanned in order to establish an overall picture of panel quality. Thus it was also possible to establish whether a relationship between attenuation and absorption exists.

Absorption Tests

Three coupons from each panel (50mm x 50mm) were taken from regions adjacent to those from which the image analysis samples were cut. They were immersed in a bath at 353K and weighed periodically over a four month period in order to produce a plot of weight gain as a function of root time. Prior to weighing each sample was towel dried. The results presented are the average of three weighing made on a Mettler balance accurate to .00005g.

In addition, plaques of cured neat resin were immersed in order to establish the saturation levels of the neat resin.

This value was used in a rule of mixtures relationship to predict the saturation levels for each panel. This analysis assumed no absorption by the fibres.

RESULTS

C-scan

The results of the T/T C-scan investigation are shown in Fig. 1. The light areas are more attenuated which implies more interaction with defects. It should be noted that the C-scans are a plan view which gives a summation of all the points through the thickness at each location. They do not give the spatial location of defects within the through thickness section.

It can be seen from Fig. 1 that the variations in the cure cycle had been successful in producing panels of different quality. Panel A is especially good whereas panel I is poor. Variations of the signal within the panels indicates inhomogeneity. This was taken into account in selecting the samples for image analysis and absorption tests. The average attenuation was recorded for each panel and is shown in Table 2.

Image Analysis

The percentage of voids for the nine panels are given in Table 2. It can be seen that void levels in the range 0% and 2.5 % have been achieved. In all comparative graphs, the results for panel I (2.5% voids) have been omitted as this is the extreme case, and its inclusion would make it difficult to separate the other results.

At present the standard method of quoting void contents is to give an average percentage void content over the entire panel. However, this gives little idea of the variation in levels across the sample. Fig. 2 shows typical void distribution in the mid-section of the panel. One more important factor which is overlooked in quoting void contents is the surface porosity. Figures 3 & 4 show micrographs of the edges (ie the surfaces) of samples with very different surface qualities. The former has a layer of resin at the surface whilst the latter is almost entirely resin starved. This extra 'surface voidage' is not detected under image analysis as the exposed fibres do not register as voids. However, under ultrasonic investigation, these surface irregularities will have an effect on the attenuation of the signal - and hence it is possible that a sample showing low void content under image analysis may show high attenuation (see panel F).

Table 2: Moisture, C-scan and image analysis results

PANEL	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
%m/%m	0.53	0.53	0.81	0.84	0.80	0.91	0.98	1.27	4.0
%Vv	0.10	0.09	0.57	1.34	1.06	0.09	0.92	1.54	2.3
Signal Ampl (αV)	2932	2486	1968	1729	1928	1469	1827	376	27
Initial Slope	0.97	1.17	1.68	1.59	1.71	1.84	1.73	4.15	7.2

Fig. 1: C-scan results, 5MHz probe

Fig. 2: Voids in centre of Panel H

Fig. 3: Resin rich surface (Panel D)

Fig. 4: Resin starved surface (Panel F)

Moisture Absorption

With the exception of panels H and I, the normalised ratio of %m/%m predicted was less than 1. It is clear that these panels had not achieved full saturation during the time of immersion. However, by looking at the absorption curves it is also obvious that panels A and B are unlikely to achieve unity. This implies that the presence of fibres within the system in some way impedes the ingress of water, and that all free volume space occupied in the neat resin system is not occupied in the woven composite. Panels H and I absorbed more water than predicted. This suggests that void filling may be taking place.

Table 2 also shows significant variations in the initial slope of the absorption curve. Panels H and I had the greatest rate of initial uptake which is consistent with their higher normalised weight gains. Given that voidage is the major variable, the results suggest that the effect of voidage is significant.

Fig. 5: Moisture absorption curves

Relationship between Attenuation and Moisture Uptake

Fig. 6: Relationship between C-scan and moisture uptake

Fig. 6 indicates that there is a relationship between attenuation and uptake. From a practical standpoint, this is encouraging as it suggests that it may well be possible to use C-scans to identify panels which will saturate quickly.

Relationship between void content and moisture uptake

The general trend is for moisture absorption to increase as void volume fraction increases (Fig 7).

Fig. 7: Void content and moisture uptake

However there are some deviations; most significantly panels F and H show higher absorptions than predicted, whereas panels D and E show lower absorptions. The results suggest either errors in the image analysis results (image analysis specimens not being representative of the panel) or that factors other than internal voids influence the absorption process. Reassessment of the image analysis results confirmed the original results and hence the influence of other factors is indicated.

DISCUSSION

Water is absorbed by [1] :

- : bulk diffusion
- : capillary action
- : diffusion into defects

Bulk diffusion is an important factor which is determined by the resin system and the degree of cure. With the possible exception of panel A which had the extra dwell in the cure cycle, the degree of cure would be expected to be the same for all the panels. Hence bulk diffusion factors are not believed to be responsible for the observed results.

Ingress due to capillary action should also be the similar for all panels since they are essentially the same in terms of volume fraction and lay-up. However, uptake due to capillary action will also depend upon the presence, location and shape of voids. Voids running parallel to fibres will facilitate capillary action whereas voids entrapped in resin rich areas will not. Although inhomogeneity in the distribution of voids was observed with some panels (D & E show local

areas of voidage), there was no strong evidence to support capillary action as being the major influence on the results.

Diffusion of moisture into voids could account for the results. However, there was no clear correlation between up-take and voidage. For example panels F & G were close to saturation whereas panels D & E which had higher void contents were not. It is interesting to compare the results of B & F which both had 0.09% voids. Panel F had a significantly higher initial slope and up-take. Clearly, factors other than void content are involved.

Panels F and H (both saturated) had high surface voidage whereas the remaining samples had lower surface voidage and/or thicker resin surface layers. The presence of voids or exposed fibres at the surface would facilitate up-take by effectively increasing the length of the diffusion front. Voids in the centre of the panels would have no effect at all until reached by the diffusion front. In the case of the panels which did not saturate, this clearly did not happen. Thus it is believed that surface quality has an important effect on moisture absorption of composites because it defines the diffusion front.

The surface quality factor also explains why the correlation between C-scan (which takes account of surface effects) and moisture absorption was better than image analysis and moisture absorption. Detailed image analysis in the surface region is required if a better correlation with moisture absorption is to be obtained.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper has shown that there is a determinable link between void content and moisture uptake - although anomalies have been observed. A much more extensive investigation of the link between void size, shape and location and the absorption of moisture is required. For industry's purposes it is worth noting that a good correlation between ultrasonic scanning and absorption levels can already be obtained, although it is first necessary obviously to account for the effects of different void free resin systems.

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